

The Influence of Agroecosystems on the Availability of Non-Timber Forest Products in Cameroon: The Case of Some Villages in Obala

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Abstract

Most anthropogenic pressures are referred to lead in the population decline of some non-timber forest products (NTFPs) species or even their loss. The aim of this study is to show the influence of agroecosystems on the availability of non-timber forest products (NTFPs) of Obala in Cameroon. Floristic inventories were carried out in 8 quadrats of 25m x 25m in Mbele and Minkama localities which are the source of the main NTFPs available in Obala. A total of 141 species of non-timber forest products belonging to 22 genera and 19 families were surveyed in three different Agroecosystems (Agroforests, Fallows land and Cultivated Fields). Euphorbiaceae and Apocynaceae are the most common families recorded. According to their characterisations, Agroforests are the most richest in species, followed by Cultivated Fields and Fallows Land. According to the stability gradient between different types of Agroecosystems, Cultivated Fields appear to be the most unstable environments, despite their diversity. This instability is thought to be the result of high population density and growing demography, which increase human pressure on non-timber forest products.

Keywords: *Non-timber forest products, anthropogenic pressure, agroecosystems, Obala.*

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Introduction

Non-timber forest products (NTFPs) remain one of the main sources of products and materials for food, health, housing and income for the population (Tchapda et al., 2022; Tajeukem et al., 2021; Guedje, 2019; Aubry & Gaüzère, 2015; Assogbadjo et al., 2005). According to a World Bank report (2002), around 90% of people living in rural areas depend on forests for their income. The current value of NTFPs to

conservationists, foresters, development stakeholders and indigenous peoples has prompted a number of initiatives aimed at promoting the sustainable use and commercialisation of NTFPs as a means of improving the well-being of rural populations, while at the same time conserving existing forests (Epanda et al., 2020 ; Fokou, 2008). Several studies have been carried out on the most utilised NTFPs in protected areas and their respective peripheries (Epanda et al., 2020 ; Guedje, 1996 ; Konsala et al., 2012 ; Tajeukem, 2017). These authors focused more on the economic, socio-cultural and medicinal aspects in the study areas, while others were more interested in the spatial distribution and quantity produced by the forest (Shackleton et al., 2015 ; Dibong et al., 2013 ; Ndangalasi et al., 2006 ; Mbolo, 2002). These include *Gnetum africanum*, *Gnetum buchholzianum*, *Iringia gabonensis*, *Garcinia lucida*, *Klainedoxa gabonensis*, *Afrastyrax lepidophylus*, *Panda oleosa*, *Cola acuminata*, *Piper capense* and others. The use of these NTFPs has become so important that it is a source of job creation (Awono et al., 2009) and generates significant income for national and even international economies.

An abundance of scientific literature has accumulated on NTFPs over the last few decades the sector's vital role in contributing to food security, poverty reduction and socio-economic in Cameroon (Tchapda et al., 2022 ; Tajeukem et al., 2021; Guedje, 2019; Bayaga et al., 2017; Bratschi et al., 2013; Aubry & Gaüzère, 2015; Jiofack et al., 2013; Ndoye et al., 1997; Tchatat et al., 2002; Mbolo, 2002; Noubissie et al., 2008). Adding value to non-timber forest products helps to conserve forest ecosystems and ensure the well-being of the people depending on them (Orou et al., 2009; Ndangalasi et al., 2006). It should be noted that initiatives to use scientific techniques to determine the availability of these products around areas where communities settle and near conservation areas are less documented. It is important to know the resources availability so that they can be better managed, conserved and developed. Most studies carried out on NTFPs in a given area use indicators that are limited to price, processing, supply chains, indigenous knowledge and distance travelled (IUCN landscape approach, Sources). As a result, no precise information is available on the abundance and distribution of NTFPs in the study areas. The present study is therefore intended to clear up this ambiguity.

The main question from this work is whether the existing floristic resources in the agroecosystems of the Obala locality provide sufficient quality and quantity of non-timber forest products to meet the socio-economic expectations of the local population. The aim of this study is to provide a directory of NTFPs available, so that their resources can be used as key element for sustainable development, management and conservation in the area.

Acquire knowledge each agroecosystem and their NTFPs is useful for developing the management and conservation plan of phylogenetic resources.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

This study was conducted in Obala, a locality situated in forest-savannah transition zone. It lies between latitude 4°10' N and longitude 11°32'. Obala is a council situated in the Lékié Division in the Centre region of Cameroon (Figure. 1). Obala has an estimated population of 78,929, or a density of 171 inhabitants per km², for a total area of 475 km², of which around 25% is urban and 75% rural (BUCREP, 2010). Due to its geographical location, Obala has a transitional equatorial climate (Suchel, 1988). This climate is characterised by an average rainfall of 1476 mm/year and an average annual temperature of about 25.5°C. The climate can be divided into 4 main seasons of varying length: a long dry season (mid-November to mid-March), a short rainy season (mid-March to the end of June), a short dry season (July to mid-August), and a long rainy season (mid-August to mid-November).

The river system is dominated by the Afamba stream, the region's main watercourse, which winds its way through a deep valley. With its many tributaries, it drains the area first in a south-easterly and north-westerly direction, then in a north-south direction until it meets the Sanaga.

Orographically, Obala is located at the heart of the South Cameroon plateau, and stands out for its position below the Yaoundé plateau. With an average altitude of 550m, the relief decreases in altitude in a South-North direction. The lowest point is in the Afamba valley at 448 m. Overall, this is a low-lying area compared with the Yaoundé region, which has an average altitude of 750m. The general morphology is slightly uneven, making it easy to develop infrastructure and agricultural activities (Bogne, 2010).

Ferralitic soils dominate the entire region. They are red or ochre (brown) and are mostly highly desaturated, i.e. acidic ($\text{pH} \leq 6$) and low in exchangeable bases (Martin, 1967; Vallérie, 1973). These soils cover most of the plateau, i.e. around 90% of the total surface area, with the exception of the valley bottoms, which are covered by hydromorphic soils more than 3 m deep.

Phytogeographically, Obala belongs to the forest-savanna transition zone of the Central Region of Cameroon. On the one hand, this is the 'semi-deciduous dense humid forest', also known as the 'Guinean-Congolian semi-caducious forest' by Letouzey (1985) or the 'semi-evergreen forest' according to White (1986). The savannahs of the region described as Guinean-Sudanese peri-forest by Aubreville (1962) are either grassy savannahs with *Imperata cylindrica* (L.) P.Beauv. (Poaceae), *Pennisetum purpureum* Schumach. (Gramineae) and *Aframomum latifolium* K.Schum (Zingiberaceae), or shrubby savannahs with *Terminalia glaucescens* Planch. ex Benth (Combretaceae) and *Bridelia ferruginea* Benth (Euphorbiaceae) according to Youta (1998). In addition, in the marshy lowlands, particularly the Afamba and Foulou rivers, there are gallery forests in flood-prone areas.

Demographically, Obala is the second largest human settlement after Yaoundé in the Centre region, with around 78,929 inhabitants (BUCREP, 2010). The importance of this human cluster is reflected both in terms of total population and density per km^2 , with an average of 100 to over 200 inhabitants per km^2 . It is a bastion of high rural population densities compared with the rest of the Central Region of Cameroon, where there is an average of 5 to 20 inhabitants per km^2 . These high densities could justify the pressure on natural resources. In view of the high population densities, agroforestry appears to be an appropriate means of conserving and protecting the environment at local and regional level.

Figure 1. Study Area

Data Collection

The following experimental set-up was used for inventory of the NTFPs available in different Agroecosystems : Quadrats measuring 25 m x 25 m were distributed over an area of 1000 m² in each Agroecosystem identified. This set-up was inspired by and improved on the one used by Kabelong et al. (2018) during floristic inventories carried out on the outskirts of Deng-Deng National Park. Once the quadrats had been installed, the NTFPs present in the quadrat were identified and counted. This activity made it possible to determine which NTFPs were present in each Agroecosystem in quality and quantity. NTFPs not identified in the field were collected properly to be identified at the Cameroon National Herbarium.

Data Analysis

The aim is to determine whether the presence and installation of agroecosystems in a given area could reduce or favour NTFP production. The methodology is based on the results obtained from the above-mentioned biological parameters used to characterise NTFPs in different types of agroecosystems, but under comparative analyses.

Agroecosystems were identified by the presence of forest trees in agricultural plantations for agroforests. Cultivated Fields were identified by the presence of a food crop or subsistence crop. In the case of fallow land, this was identified by the presence of a crop that had been left uncultivated for 3 or 5 years.

Microsoft Excel® 2013 was used to enter and code the data, on the basis of a tabulation grid, which enable the data to be analysed by migrating towards the objectives of the study. The data was then exported to SPSS.v 20.0 software from International Business Machine Corporation (IBM) for statistical testing. The cross-tabulations and frequency analyses were imported into Microsoft's Excel spreadsheet program to produce the graphs. Several types of analysis were carried out according to the specific objectives of the study. The statistical analyses were carried out using XLSTAT 20.4 software.

Results

Availability of Non-Timber Forest Products by the Agro-Ecosystems Studied

In the locality of Obala, the villages Mbele and Minkama are considered as origin collection points of the majority of NTFPs in the town. The use of scientific approach to determine the availability of NTFPs around areas is obtain Table 1. This shows precise information on the availability of non-timber forest products according to Agroecosystem types, in the Mbele and Minkama sites. Three types of agroecosystems were inventoried in the Minkama and Mbele sites: Agroforests, Fallows land and Cultivated Fields land. from these Agroecosystems, Agroforests are the most richness and diverse, followed by Cultivated Fields and Fallow land. A total of 141 species of non-timber forest products belonging to 22 genera and 19 families were recorded in these Agroecosystems. Euphorbiaceae and Apocynaceae appear to be the most diverse families.

Table 1. Agroecosystems and NTFPs Surveyed at the Mbele and Minkama Sites

Agroecosystems	Families	Species	Number
Agroforests	Anacardiaceae	<i>Trichoscypha acuminata</i>	1
	Annonaceae	<i>Annickia chlorantha</i>	2
	Apocynaceae	<i>Alstonia boonei</i>	1
	Apocynaceae	<i>Picralima nitida</i>	2
	Arecaceae	<i>Raphia sp</i>	6

	Burseraceae	<i>Dacryodes edulis</i>	2
	Burseraceae	<i>Dacryodes macrophylla</i>	1
	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Ricinodendron heudelotii</i>	1
	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Hevea brasiliensis</i>	1
	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Allanblackia floribunda</i>	1
	Irvingiaceae	<i>Irvingia gabonensis</i>	2
	Lamiaceae	<i>Vitex doniana</i>	1
	Marantaceae	<i>Marantochloa manii</i>	5
	Mimosaceae	<i>Tetrapleura tetraptera</i>	3
	Moraceae	<i>Ficus mucoso</i>	2
	Myristicaceae	<i>Pycnanthus angolensis</i>	1
	Sterculiaceae	<i>Cola sp.</i>	2
	Sterculiaceae	<i>Cola pachycarpa</i>	1
	Sterculiaceae	<i>Cola acuminata</i>	2
	Zygophyllaceae	<i>Balanites wilsoniana</i>	3
Cultivated Fields	Annonaceae	<i>Annickia chlorantha</i>	2
	Apocynaceae	<i>Alstonia boonei</i>	1
	Apocynaceae	<i>Picalima nitida</i>	1
	Arecaceae	<i>Raphia sp</i>	4
	Burseraceae	<i>Dacryodes macrophylla</i>	1
	Dioscoreaceae	<i>Dioscorea bulbifera</i>	8
	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Dicoglypemma caloneura</i>	2
	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Ricinodendron heudelotii</i>	1
	Gnetaceae	<i>Gnetum africanum</i>	10
	Malvaceae	<i>Cola acuminata</i>	1
	Marantaceae	<i>Marantochloa manii</i>	10
	Moraceae	<i>Ficus sp</i>	1
	Sterculiaceae	<i>Cola nitida</i>	1
	Urticaceae	<i>Myrianthus arboreus</i>	1
	Zingiberaceae	<i>Aframomum augustifolium</i>	15
	Zygophyllaceae	<i>Balanites wilsoniana</i>	1
Fallow land	Anacardiaceae	<i>Trichoscypha acuminata</i>	1
	Annonaceae	<i>Annickia chlorantha</i>	2
	Apocynaceae	<i>Alstonia boonei</i>	1
	Dioscoreaceae	<i>Dioscorea bulbifera</i>	1
	Gnetaceae	<i>Gnetum africanum</i>	8
	Irvingiaceae	<i>Irvingia gabonensis</i>	2
	Lamiaceae	<i>Vitex doniana</i>	1
	Marantaceae	<i>Marantochloa manii</i>	7
	Mimosaceae	<i>Tetrapleura tetraptera</i>	1
	Sterculiaceae	<i>Cola nitida</i>	1
	Urticaceae	<i>Myrianthus arboreus</i>	1
	Zingiberaceae	<i>Aframomum augustifolium</i>	15
Total			141

Influence of Agroecosystems Installation on the Availability and Production of NTFPs

Number of species per type of Agroecosystem

According to the stability gradient between the different types of Agroecosystems, the Fields Land are more unstable environments, although they are diversified. On average, there is one species per Agroecosystem type (Figure. 2). This could be explained by the fact that population density, and consequently pressure on non-timber forest products, is higher in some agroecosystems than others.

Figure 2. Number of Species According to Agroecosystem

Analysis of the Structural Parameters of the Agroecosystems Surveyed

These analyses are based on Relative Abundance (DeR), Relative Density (DoR), Relative Frequency (Fr) and Importance Value Index (IVI) in Table 2.

According to Table 2, Relative Abundance is 8.33% for fallow land, 6.25% for Cultivated Fields and 5.00% for Agroforests. Relative density (DoR) was 0.55% in Fallow land, 0.60% in Cultivated Fields 0.32% in Agroforests. Relative Frequency (Fr) shows the same values as relative abundance for the different types of Agroecosystems surveyed. This means that the dynamics are more stable in Fallow land than in Cultivated Fields and Agroforests, which are frequently disturbed.

The Importance Value Index (IVI) of Curtis and Macintosh (1951) was calculated for the different types of Agroecosystems. Analysis of Table 2 shows that, overall, the Agroecosystems with the highest IVI are Fallows Land (17.21%), followed by Cultivated Fields (13.10%) and Agro-forests (10.32%). In other words, fallow land is the least disturbed environment, with a low level of human activity and a much more stable dynamic. Compared to fallow land, fields land and agroforests are environments undergoing perpetual change (regular clearing, change of crop per season, etc.) and presenting a much greater dynamic.

Table 2. Variation in Diversity Indices as a Function of Agroecosystems

	DeR	DoR	Fr	IVI
Agroforests	5,00%	0,32%	5,00%	10,32%
Cultivated Fields	6,25%	0,60%	6,25%	13,10%
Fallow Land	8,33%	0,55%	8,33%	17,21%

Abundance of individuals by species according to type of Agroecosystem

The dynamics of the appearance of individuals by type of Agroecosystems is greater in Cultivated Fields, less in Fallows Land and Agroforests (Figure. 3). According to this graph, Agroforests are the least disturbed Agroecosystems with very low dynamics. They are followed by Fallow Land, which has a fairly stable dynamic. Cultivated Fields, due to farming activities and crop variations, are Agroecosystems that are regularly disturbed and show strong dynamics. This explains the low abundance of non-timber forest products in the Cultivated Fields and their richness in the Agroforests system.

Figure. 3. Dynamics of Appearance of NTFP Individuals by Type of Agroecosystems

Discussion

Available Non-Timber Forest Products by Agroecosystem

In the study area, the Agroecosystems most present and richness in species are Agroforests, followed by Cultivated Fields and Fallows Land. This result is in line with those of Pousse et al. (2011), who present Cultivated Fields as an Agroecosystem with a very disturbed vegetation potential due to the practice of slash-and-burn agriculture and which is a very devastating method. Moreover, according to Cerutti & Tacconi (2006), the areas where shifting cultivation is regularly practised have often been blamed for the alarming deforestation of tropical rainforests, leading to the modification of NTFP habitats and their subsequent disappearance.

As far as Fallow Land is concerned, the low availability of NTFPs is due to the fact that a very small variety of NTFP, such as *Ricinodendron heudelottii*, grows best only in degraded areas (Fallow Land). At Pallisco in the East Cameroon region, Anonymous (2008) also observed an increase in this species in areas degraded by machinery and fallow land.

For Agroforests, Tchatchou et al. (2015), in their work on the state of play, current causes and prospects for deforestation and forest degradation in the Congo Basin, also mention that Agroforests are the richest and most diverse environments for NTFPs, although the number of trees is declining.

Influence of Agroecosystems Establishment on Availability and Production

Number of species according to Agroecosystems

According to the stability gradient between the different types of Agroecosystem, the Cultivated Fields are more unstable environments, although they are diversified. There is an average of one species per Agroecosystem type, with an equitability of 0.76 for Agroforests, 0.58 for Fallows Land and 0.66 for Cultivated Fields. These results are at odds with the definition of Odum (1979) cited by Sonké (1998). For these authors, Agroecosystems that have reached a level of maturity and are not subject to disruptive constraints have a high equitability, of the order of 0.6 to 0.8. Agroecosystems that are in a transitional state or under stress have low equitability. According to Dajoz cit. Sonké (op. cit.), low equitability means that a few dominant species are very important. Agroforests have the highest equitability (0.76) while Cultivated Fields have a low equitability (0.66). The equitability value obtained in the fields is at odds with Odum's definition. Cultivated Fields are subject to frequent disturbances and cannot be classified as stable agroecosystems.

Analysis of the structural parameters of the agroecosystems surveyed

Analysis of the structural parameters reveals that, overall, the Agroecosystems with the highest IVI are Fallow Land (17.21%), followed by Cultivated Fields (13.10%) and Agroforests (10.32%). This result is similar to those of Kengne et al. (2024) in Diamaré, Far North Cameroon, who believe that fallow farming in Agroecosystems over the years has contributed to the conservation of many tree species with multiple uses. However, the practice of agriculture without fallow considerably reduces species richness and modifies the composition of the original flora of a locality.

Bondé et al. (2013) found that, in agrosystem formations in Burkina Faso, only utilitarian species are not completely cut down during the opening up of fields and the establishment of Agroecosystems. Anthropogenic practices that retain only woody species selected for their role in agroforestry systems lead to the homogenisation of plant communities. Other authors, such as Sina et al. (2016) and Awé et al. (2021), have also pointed out that the reduced number of woody species observed is linked to the strong selection and choice of plant species that will be kept, maintained or cut down during the preparation and installation of agroecosystems.

Abundance of individuals by species according to the type of agroecosystem

NTFP species richness is highest in Agroforests, which are the least disturbed Agroecosystems with very low dynamics. They are followed by Fallow Land, where the dynamics are fairly stable. Cultivated Fields, due to farming activities and crop variations, are Agroecosystems that are regularly disturbed and show strong dynamics. This explains the low abundance of non-timber forest products in the Cultivated Fields and their richness in the Agroforests. These results are similar as those of Tonga et al. (2017) who, in their work on the availability of fundamental NTFPs on the periphery of the Lobeke National Park, presented Agro-forests as the Agroecosystems harbouring more NTFPs. For these authors, in terms of densities, diameter classes and types of environment, Agroforests are the Agroecosystems with the most NTFPs.

Conclusion

The general objective of the study on the influence of Agroecosystems on the availability of non-timber forest products in the Obala locality in the Central Region of Cameroon was to identify NTFPs in the Agroecosystems of the Obala locality. As for the results, 141 species of non-timber forest products belonging to 22 genera and 19 families were identified in three different Agroecosystems. Euphorbiaceae and Apocynaceae are the most diverse families. Agroforests, Fallows Land and Cultivated Fields are the three types of Agroecosystems inventoried in Obala. The richness of NTFPs is greater in Agroforests than in Fallows Land and even less in Cultivated Fields. Thus, the Obala Agroecosystems are home to NTFPs that can be characterised. Non-timber forest products are more abundant and more diversified in Agroforests and Fallows Land, and less abundant and less diversified in Cultivated Fields. Thus, the installation and presence of Agroecosystems has an influence on the availability and production of NTFPs in the Obala locality.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interests.

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